

IMPROVED MECHANISM OF THE DIGITAL QUALITY MANAGEMENT MODEL OF EDUCATION IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract: In this article we will consider the application of innovative methods of the digital environment in preschool educational organizations. We will study what innovative approaches and technologies can be used to improve the accessibility, efficiency and quality of education in preschool educational institutions. We will also discuss the advantages and risks of using digital tools and resources in preschool education, as well as consider examples of successful implementation of innovative methods in the practice of preschool education.

Keywords: innovative methods, digital environment, preschool education, accessibility, efficiency, quality, educational process, educational technologies, interactive methods, digital resources, games, applications, multimedia materials, virtual reality, augmented reality, online platforms, educational resources.

Introduction: In the modern world, digital technologies are playing an increasingly important role in various spheres of our lives. One of these areas is education, including preschool education. In this regard, there is a need to improve the quality management mechanisms of education in preschool educational organizations.

The use of innovative methods of the digital environment in the management of preschool educational organizations (pre-school) has a huge potential for improving the quality of education and the effectiveness of organizations. In this article, we will look at various aspects of this topic and analyze the advantages and challenges associated with the use of digital innovations in the management of preschool institutions.

One of the main advantages of using innovative methods of the digital environment in the management of preschool educational organizations is to increase the efficiency and accessibility of education. Digital technologies make it possible to automate and optimize management processes, such as electronic

document management, schedule planning, resource monitoring, and others. This helps to save time and improve the accuracy of administrative tasks.

In addition, innovative methods of the digital environment provide new opportunities for learning and development of children. The use of interactive educational programs, applications, multimedia materials and other digital resources makes the educational process more interesting and attractive for children.

Fig. 1. Management conditions in the conditions of digitalization of a preschool educational organization

They can get access to a variety of educational materials, games and tasks that contribute to the development of various skills and knowledge, including logical thinking, creative thinking, communication and others. To date, two approaches to informatization of the organization of preschool education have become widespread. The first approach is that the organization of preschool education is presented as a multifunctional organization.

At the same time, its managerial financial and economic activities are automated: accounting, material and technical accounting, personnel accounting. The second approach is based on the informatization of the educational process, in which the development of the information environment of preschool education is carried out through the informatization of pedagogical activity (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1 shows three main stages of information process management: collecting information about the state of the organization of preschool education and the external environment; processing and analyzing information; providing information about the order.

However, the application of innovative methods of the digital environment can also present challenges and risks. For example, it is necessary to ensure the security and confidentiality of data, protection from unwanted content and abuse of technology. It is also important to take into account the individual needs and characteristics of each child so that the use of digital technologies corresponds to their age and development.

The advantages and challenges of applying digital innovations should be carefully studied and taken into account for the successful management of preschool educational organizations. The digital environment provides a wide range of tools and resources that can be successfully applied in preschool education. One of the main advantages of using digital technologies is to increase the availability of education. With the help of online platforms, websites and applications, children can get an education anytime and anywhere. This is especially important for children who cannot attend preschool for various reasons, such as illness or remote location.

In conclusion, the use of innovative methods of the digital environment in the management of preschool educational organizations can significantly improve the quality and accessibility of education. However, in order to achieve optimal results, careful planning, training and support from the administration and teaching staff are necessary.

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